

Baseline wind farms/ D1.1

WP1, T1.1

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Executive summary

This report is deliverable D1.1 in the EU funded project SUDOCO (grant agreement 101122256). The report provides information on the initial developments and utilization of two different coupling frameworks.

First, the Dynamiks framework couples the high-fidelity flow solver EllipSys3D to the high-fidelity aero-servo-elastic tool HAWC2 to provide detailed simulations of the flow inside large wind farms and the performance and loads experienced by each turbine. Dynamiks has been employed to build a large LES database for two wind farms, the CL-Windcon 3×3 and the Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN), for a range of different atmospheric conditions. The report contains a high-level presentation of some key results of the database.

Second, an open-source coupling framework has been implemented to connect individual wind turbine controllers to an overarching wind farm controller. The framework is tested and a tutorial is provided.

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1 Introduction

The overall aim of the SUDOCO project (“SUstainable resilient Data-enabled Off-shore wind farm and control CO-design”) is to develop the **Control Room of the Future**. This control room will allow real-time optimization of wind farm performance by considering both power production and the structural health of turbines across their lifetimes, optimizing for monetary and ecological metrics, for example.

SUDOCO will employ a range of different numerical tools to provide accurate modelling of both the wind farm wake aerodynamics and the aero-servo-elastic turbine response required to achieve the overall aim. State-of-the-art tools for wake aerodynamics and loads will be fully integrated and coupled to provide the necessary estimation of their complex interaction and guide the operation through an overarching wind farm controller.

The deliverable at hand is the first in its work package and contains two main contributions, laying the foundations for high-fidelity simulation studies on the various control concepts:

1. The implementation of software coupling between a high-fidelity flow field solver and an aero-servo-elastic turbine simulation tool. This coupled simulation framework consequently is utilized to construct a large database of baseline wind farm simulations. Throughout the remainder of this project, these simulations will be used to train models and then to benchmark wind farm control algorithms in the same simulation set-up.
2. The implementation and an extensive tutorial of a coupling framework that links individual wind turbine controllers with a wind-farm-level controller. This software platform will be used in following deliverables to develop wind farm control algorithms in various programming languages (Python, MATLAB) and directly link them to various high-fidelity simulation tools.

1.1 Numerical Tools

Numerical tools are frequently classified in terms of fidelity, from low to high, which usually also classify the computational costs involved for model evaluation. A brief introduction to the numerical tools used to simulate wind farm flows and wind farm performance is given here, but we refer to Porté-Agel et al., [2020](#) for a more detailed and broader overview.

Low-fidelity engineering wake models provide estimates of power production by modelling steady state wake aerodynamics (Porté-Agel et al., 2020). These models can not be used for load estimation, as accurate loads modeling requires an accurate reproduction of the turbulent flow structures, which these models lack.

Turbulent inflow can be estimated using mid-fidelity tools such as the so-called "Mann boxes" (Mann, 1994; Mann, 1998) for free-standing wind turbines or the Dynamic Wake Meandering (DWM) model (Larsen et al., 2007; Larsen et al., 2008) for turbines operating in wake. The mid-fidelity arises due to the simplifying assumptions of DWM, that turbulent scales can be separated and that the wake acts as a passive tracer. This allows DWM to combine engineering wake models with added turbulence and large scale meandering derived from Mann turbulent boxes, which are computationally fast and mimic wake aerodynamics with some limitations. DWM has been implemented for full farm scale simulations in FAST.Farm (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021) and HAWC2Farm (Liew et al., 2022; Liew, 2022).

High-fidelity simulations using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) do not have the same restrictive assumptions, but are computationally expensive and can not provide accurate estimations in real time. State-of-the-art CFD models capture the dynamics utilizing Large Eddy Simulations (LES), which resolve the largest turbulent structures and models the effects of the smallest. SUDOCO will employ high-fidelity flow solvers like AMR-Wind (Sprague et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2024) and Ellip-Sys3D (Michelsen, 1992; Michelsen, 1994; Sørensen, 1995) to provide turbulent inflow, which serve as input to aero-servo-elastic tools.

The turbines are modelled with aero-servo-elastic tools, such as OpenFAST (Jonkman, 2013) developed at National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and HAWC2 (Larsen and Hansen, 2007) developed at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU). FAST/OpenFAST and HAWC2 provide estimates of power production, aerodynamic loads and deflections, when subject to turbulent inflow and serve as the interface for individual wind turbine controllers.

In this report, Ellipsys3D will be utilized for the flow solver, while the turbines will be modelled using HAWC2. The communication between flow and turbines will be facilitated through a new multi-fidelity-coupling framework being developed at DTU named **Dynamiks**¹, which is outlined in Section 2.1.4.

1.2 Wind farm controller

The continuous optimization of the turbine performance in pursuit of a farm-wide optimal target requires the coordination of individual turbine controllers through a wind farm control algorithm. The challenge with this is that the range of simulation platforms and tools outlined in Section 1.1 will often be implemented in different

¹<https://dynamiks.pages.windenergy.dtu.dk/dynamiks/>

programming languages and software environments. Having to translate each wind farm control algorithm into a tool- and language-compatible format for each simulation software is intractable. Therefore, one of the key deliverables in WP1 of the SUDOCO project is a modular wind farm control software platform, which can be utilized for both mid- and high-fidelity simulations. This interface is to be independent of the local platform (Linux, Windows, ...) and programming language of choice (Python, MATLAB, Java, ...).

To prevent having to develop a new Application Programming Interface (API) for each simulation platform, we instead focus on a common “point of communication” that can be used across simulation tools. A common standard for wind turbine control was established in the early 2010s by DNV GL and a new version release of their Bladed wind turbine simulation tool (OffshoreWIND.biz, 2013; Hassan, 2013). The Bladed version 4.4 release in March 2013 brought the users the “DISCON” turbine controller signal format, allowing users to run custom wind turbine controller algorithms as long as they followed the DISCON and “swap variable” conventions. These “swap variables” define how the measurements and control setpoints are encoded between the turbine simulation platform and the turbine controller.

Since 2013, the usage of the bladed-style DISCON turbine controllers has become widespread. Most high-fidelity simulation platform nowadays can accept DISCON-style turbine controllers. For example, AMRWind, SOWFA and OpenFAST are all compatible with Bladed-style turbine controllers. Additionally, TU Berlin’s QBlade is also compatible with Bladed-style turbine controllers (Marten et al., 2024). DTU’s HAWC2 code has already been coupled with Bladed-style turbine controllers in the past (Rinker, 2021).

Thus, the most logical point of entry for a wind farm controller is through the (Bladed-style) wind turbine controllers. These wind turbine controllers are inherently modular and can, without modification, be used across various simulation tools. Additionally, these turbine controllers also receive measurements from the turbine simulation platform, and assign turbine control setpoints in the exact same format across simulation platforms. This makes it the perfect contender for a modular wind farm controller extension.

Recently, Mulders and Wingerden, 2018 presented the Delft Research Controller (DRC), which is an open-source and DISCON-style wind turbine controller to be freely used across academia. Consequently, Abbas et al., 2022a expanded and matured the open-source DRC code, naming their variant ROSCO (NREL, 2024). Since 2022, the usage of ROSCO has become favoured in- and outside of academia, notably due to its inclusion of state-of-the-art functionality such as automated controller tuning. For these reasons, the work at hand proceeds to implement the wind farm controller infrastructure in ROSCO.

2 Methods

2.1 High Fidelity Wind Farm Flow Simulations

2.1.1 Flow Simulator

All high-fidelity wind farm flow simulations in the database have been performed using the DTU in-house flow solver EllipSys3D (Michelsen, 1994; Michelsen, 1992; Sørensen, 1995), a three-dimensional multi-block incompressible Navier-Stokes solver which expresses the governing equations in general curvilinear coordinates and solves with a finite volume method in a collocated grid. A second-order accurate three-level implicit method is used for time advancement, which includes sub-iterations within each time step. The pressure correction is solved with a SIMPLEC approach (Shen et al., 2003; Kobayashi and Pereira, 1991) and Rhie/Chow interpolation avoids odd/even decoupling. A fourth-order central differencing scheme which includes a fourth-order dissipation term to reduce numerical instabilities is used to discretise convective terms (Wit and Rhee, 2013). For non-neutral atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) simulations including temperature effects, the potential temperature transport equation is also solved and Monin-Obukhov similarity theory (Monin and Obukhov, 1954) is applied at the lowest grid cell to calculate the instantaneous surface shear stress.

Turbulence modelling is achieved using Large Eddy Simulations (LES), which explicitly resolves all turbulent scales larger than the filter size (usually equivalent to the grid size) and models all smaller scales. This means that it is the highest fidelity modelling tool feasible for conducting simulations of wind farm flows and accurately captures the development and influence of large-scale energy-transporting turbulence. In this work, sub-grid scales are represented using the Anisotropic Minimum-Dissipation (AMD) model by Abkar et al., 2016.

2.1.2 Inflow Modelling

Prior to the wind farm simulations, a precursor atmospheric boundary layer (ABL) simulation is conducted without the farm present, in order to generate the atmospheric flow which is then used as inflow in the successor simulations of the wind farm. In the precursor simulations, surface temperature, geostrophic wind, and surface roughness are specified along with initial conditions of temperature profile, and the flow is recycled through a very large domain and allowed to develop over time, before planes are extracted and used as the inflow to the successor simulation. The

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flow is aligned with the streamwise direction at hub height by utilizing a wind direction controller. More information on conducting non-neutral ABL simulations in EllipSys3D can be found in Hodgson et al., 2023a.

2.1.3 Wind Turbine Modelling

Wind turbines are modelled using the actuator disc (Mikkelsen, 2004), which represents the effect of a wind turbine on the flow by applying body forces inside the computational domain. The applied forces are spread over a disc representing the rotor area. The magnitude of the body forces and the positions at which they are applied are determined through a coupling with an aeroelastic solver, which also provides the entire structural response of the turbine to the flow simulated in LES. The aero-servo-elastic solver used for these simulations is HAWC2 (Larsen and Hansen, 2007), a multi-body finite-element solver which uses Timoshenko beam theory and therefore models the effect of both bending and torsional deflection, important for very large turbines such as the IEA22MW simulated here. The IEA22MW has a rated power of 22 MW at 11 m/s and a radius of $R = 142.0$ m (Zahle et al., 2024a; Zahle et al., 2024b).

2.1.4 Dynamiks: Multi-fidelity Coupling Framework

The coupling between flow solver (EllipSys3D) and aeroelastic solver (HAWC2) is achieved with the recently developed Dynamiks framework, a general flow-aero-servo-elastic coupling framework written in Python by main developer Mads Mølgaard Pedersen and thoroughly tested by Niels Trolborg, Emily Louise Hodgson, and Søren Juhl Andersen. As demonstrated by the diagram in Figure 2.1, EllipSys3D is first advanced by one timestep and the flow solved; then velocities are extracted at the turbine blade locations and sent to Dynamiks, which passes them to HAWC2. HAWC2 uses the velocities to calculate the blade forces and deflections, which are returned to Dynamiks and used to set the actuators forces and locations within EllipSys3D. This means that the effect of blade deflection on the flow is modelled (see Hodgson et al., 2021 for a discussion of the effect of flexibility). A turbine controller is also included, which allows the rotational speed and blade pitch of the turbine to change in response to the dynamic inflow variations.

2.1.5 Simulation Setup

Precursor Simulations

The initial precursor simulations were generated as part of the FLOW project¹, while additional runs were performed specifically for SUDOCO to accom-

¹<https://www.flow-horizon.eu/>

Figure 2.1: Dynamics coupling schematic showing communication, main transferred variables and order of operations for time advancement in a simulation which couples EllipSys3D and HAWC2.

moderate the use of the IEA22MW wind turbine. The simulations were performed on an equidistant grid of $10,240\text{m} \times 10,240\text{m} \times 3,000\text{m}$ with a total of $512 \times 512 \times 384$ cells. This corresponds to $dx = dy = 20\text{m}$, where x corresponds to streamwise direction and y the lateral direction, and $dz = 5$ (where z is the vertical direction) up to $z = 1500\text{m}$, above which the grid is stretched until the top domain boundary.

The surface temperature is set to 288.15K , temperature at the top of 298.48K , geostrophic wind of 10m/s , and surface roughness of $1 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{m}$. Two different initial ABL heights are simulated for the CNBL, namely 150m and 500m . The simulations are run for 20 hours to develop the flow, before extracting and storing 2 hours worth of data for the wind farm simulations. The resulting profiles of velocity magnitude and turbulence intensity are shown in Figure 2.2. Turbulence intensity (TI) is calculated as $TI = (\sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k})/U_{hub}$, where k is the turbulent kinetic energy, $k = 0.5(u'^2 + v'^2 + w'^2)$,

and u' , v' and w' are the fluctuating velocity components and U_{hub} is the velocity magnitude at hub height. The velocity profiles have a well-defined velocity gradient at the inversion height, and for the lower case of 150m the turbines will be operating partly above the inversion and experience a large vertical velocity gradient. Such atmospheric conditions were identified as particularly challenging for modern and future large wind turbines, as little is known about turbines operating above the inversion layer. The turbulence intensity for both cases is also low, 2.2% and 3.0% respectively at hub height for the 150m and 500m CNBLs. It is also evident how the inversion height develops so that the final height is above the initial height of both 150m and 500m, although the former has a larger growth. It should also be noted that the 150m case is particularly challenging to model numerically due to the refinement criteria (Sullivan and Patton, 2011), which is not fully satisfied due to computational limitations. More information on conducting non-neutral ABL simulations in EllipSys3D can be found in Hodgson et al., 2023a.

Figure 2.2: Time- and horizontally-averaged profiles of the CNBL precursors with initial inversion height of 150m and 500m: A) Velocity Magnitude U_{mag} ; B) Turbulence Intensity, $TI = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k}/U_{mag}$. The rotor area is shown in grey for comparison.

Wind Farm Simulations

To perform the wind farm simulations, planes extracted from the precursor simulation are applied on the inlet of the successor domain, which contains the wind farm. Two wind farms are simulated: the CL-Windcon reference wind farm, which is a regular 3×3 wind farm with lateral spacing of 10R and streamwise spacing of 14R, and a subset of the Hollandse Kust Noord (HKN) wind farm². The fullscale HKN

²<https://www.crosswindhkn.nl/>

wind farm consists of a total of 69 wind turbines with a rated capacity of 11MW, but here only a subset of 10 wind turbines in an irregular layout are considered due to computational constraints. The IEA22MW wind turbine is used for both wind farm layouts, which are scaled geometrically according to the turbine radius. The computational grid used for these two wind farms is identical as they have similar total areas. The total extent of the computational domain is $10,240\text{m} \times 10,240\text{m} \times 3,000\text{m}$. The extent is the same as the precursor, but two different successor domains are created, one for the CL-Windcon and one for the scaled HKN. The successor domain for CL-Windcon has a total of $768 \times 768 \times 384$ cells, while the successor for HKN has $1024 \times 705 \times 384$ cells. Both grids have a refined region where the turbines are located. The refined central region is located from $x = 0\text{m}$ to $x = 5,991\text{m}$ for CL-Windcon and to $x = 7,500\text{m}$ for HKN, as well as $y = 2,520\text{m}$ to $y = 7,720\text{m}$, and $z = 0\text{m}$ to $z = 1,500\text{m}$ which are equal for the two grids. This yields an equidistant grid resolution of $dx = dy = 8.87\text{m}$, $dz = 5\text{m}$ for both grids. This corresponds to 16 horizontal cells per rotor radius. The block structure of EllipSys3D enables easy grid studies, which is important part of any CFD study. Therefore, the simulations have also been run on the same grid, but $2\times$ and $4\times$ coarser. Figure 2.3 shows the two wind farm layouts as well as the full computational domain and the equidistant region for flow coming from left to right is shown in broken and dotted lines for the CL-Windcon and HKN wind farm, respectively. The HKN wind farm has been rotated for flow coming from South-West, which is the predominant wind direction as shown in D3.1 from SUDOCO, which analysed the reference scenarios³. The different wind directions for the scaled CL-Windcon wind farm are achieved by rotating counterclockwise around the center turbine. The full domain is significantly larger than the wind farms to reduce numerical blockage to a minimum, which can otherwise significantly influence the flow solution.

A total of 36 simulations were run, corresponding to 30 simulations of the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm and 6 simulations of the HKN wind farm. The simulations that were conducted are listed in Table 2.1, showing the wind farm, boundary layer height ($2\times$), wind direction, and horizontal grid resolution ($3\times$).

³https://sudoco.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/D3.1_Reference-Scenarios.pdf

Figure 2.3: Wind farm layouts of CL-Windcon in red squares and scaled HKN, where the modelled subset of 10 turbines are marked in fully colored blue circles, while the remaining part of the HKN is shown with blue circles. The full computational domain is shown in the box with the full line and the broken and dotted lines indicates the equidistant region for the CL-Windcon and HKN wind farm simulations respectively.

Wind Farm	BL height [m]	Wind Direction [°]	Resolution R/dy
CL-Windcon 3x3	150, 500	0	4, 8, 16
CL-Windcon 3x3	150, 500	15	4, 8, 16
CL-Windcon 3x3	150, 500	30	4, 8, 16
CL-Windcon 3x3	150, 500	45	4, 8, 16
CL-Windcon 3x3	150, 500	90	4, 8, 16
HKN	150, 500	South-West	4, 8, 16

Table 2.1: Wind Farm Simulation Cases

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2.2 Wind Farm Controller

The **Control Room of the Future** requires direct interaction between the above high-fidelity flow and turbine modelling tools and a wind farm controller. The initial implementation of the wind farm controller is described here.

2.3 Introducing ZeroMQ: the communication interface between ROSCO and an external wind farm controller

The envisioned information flow between turbine controllers and an external wind farm controller is sketched out in Figure 2.4. The wind farm flow simulator is shown on the left, which could correspond to Dynamiks. In principle, the wind farm simulator includes a wind turbine model for each wind turbine in the simulation, typically simulated by an aero-elastic code like OpenFAST or HAWC2. Inside each wind turbine simulation, the turbine control is delegated through the Bladed-style DISCON controller interface, e.g., using ROSCO. Thus, each wind turbine runs its own instance of ROSCO. Each of these ROSCO instances sends turbine measurements to the wind farm controller and receives control setpoints from the wind farm controller at regular time intervals.

The communication between the turbine controllers and wind farm controller is facilitated by the ZeroMQ protocol. ZeroMQ is an open-source universal messaging library which can transmit information bidirectionally across different software and across various platforms. ZeroMQ has been successfully used in the past for coupling high-fidelity simulations in SOWFA to external wind farm controllers in Python (TUDelft, 2019b) and MATLAB (TUDelft, 2019a) at the Delft University of Technology.

Figure 2.4: Information flowchart for wind farm controller interface. Each turbine simulator includes an independent turbine controller implemented according to the Bladed-style DISCON interface. Each of these turbine controllers sends measurements to the wind farm controller and receives control setpoints from the wind farm controller at regular time intervals.

Here, the server/client messaging pattern from ZeroMQ is implemented. The wind farm controller is called the “server”, and the ROSCO instances (one for each turbine) are called “clients”. The server opens a connection with each client across a network port across which the information is exchanged, e.g.,

```
network_address = "tcp://*:5555"
```

By communicating across a network port, this means that, in theory, the wind farm controller can run on a different computer than the system on which the high-fidelity simulation is running. Additionally, the communication interface takes in the order of milliseconds to send and receive information. This makes this framework particularly scalable.

2.3.1 ZeroMQ client in ROSCO

For a thorough understanding of this subsection, the reader is required to have a basic understanding of the ROSCO controller (please see Abbas et al., 2022b and the documentation of ROSCO⁴). The implementation of ZeroMQ in ROSCO originates from work by Bart Doekemeijer in October 2021, while employed at NREL (Doekemeijer, 2021a; Doekemeijer, 2021b). However, this initial version was never validated or matured such that it could be used across simulation platforms by the wider research community. In November 2023, during work for the SUDOCO project, discussions with NREL took place and the revisions to the ZeroMQ implementation in ROSCO were initiated and performed by NREL (Gupta, 2023).

The ZeroMQ interface in ROSCO transmits, by default, a set of measurements to the wind farm controller interface. These measurements include a turbine identification number, the turbine’s status, clock time, power, generator speed, rotor speed, generator torque, nacelle heading, vane heading, out-of-plane bending moments, and the azimuth angle. These measurements are gathered by ROSCO in a single string, where each measurement is depicted in Scientific (exponential) notation and 6 digits, typically coded as “%.6e”, and comma separated. The code on the server side should decode this message into integer/float variables so that they can be used in the chosen wind farm control algorithm. The default setpoints that the wind farm controller sends to ROSCO are then assigned internally as the control target setpoints. The setpoints may include a generator torque (offset), a nacelle heading (offset), and a pitch angle (offset) for each blade. These setpoints are decoded with as “%016.5f”, implying 16 resp. 5 digits before the number separator.

⁴<https://rosc0.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

The ZeroMQ communication protocol in ROSCO is enabled in the DISCON.IN input file, by setting the option “ZMQ_Mode” under the category “CONTROLLER FLAGS” to 1. Additionally, the control degrees of freedom that the wind farm control algorithm is trying to control must also be enabled. For example, for wake steering, then yaw control must be enabled by setting “Y_ControlMode” to 1.

Additionally, the ZeroMQ-specific options must be assigned:

- “ZMQ_CommAddress” – the communication address over which the ROSCO controllers and the wind farm controller will exchange information. The recommended value is `network_address = "tcp://*:5555"`, implying that the communication happens on the local computer over network port 5555.
- “ZMQ_UpdatePeriod” – the update period of ZeroMQ. Even though the ZeroMQ network communication only takes a couple of milliseconds, it can still slow down the code if it is called at the same sampling rate as the aero-elastic simulation code. Additionally, the wind farm controller usually only requires to be called every second or even every minute. To reduce unnecessary time wasted in communication, the update period can be specified here. The default value is 2, meaning the wind farm controller and ROSCO communicate every 2 seconds.
- “ZMQ_ID” – the turbine identification number. Multiple turbines communicate over the same network port, and therefore this variable must be set to a unique turbine number so that the wind farm controller can identify which measurements belong to which turbine. This number should be set equal to the turbine index in the simulation.

2.3.2 ZeroMQ server

With the ZeroMQ client in ROSCO completed, there must also be a ZeroMQ server for the chosen wind farm controller code. Example codes for ZeroMQ servers in various programming languages are available in the corresponding documentation, e.g., Python, C, Java.

For Python, ROSCO readily includes a wind farm controller class that can be used to facilitate the ZeroMQ interface. An example of its usage is shown in Figure 2.5, where the wind farm controller applies the following logic:

1. All turbines default to a yaw offset of 0.0 deg.
2. All turbines default to a blade pitch angle of 0.645 deg.
3. If the simulation time is larger than 10 seconds, the yaw offset of the first turbine is set to 20.0 degrees.


```

import os
import numpy as np
from roscotoolbox.control_interface import wfc_zmq_server

class wfc_controller():
    def __init__(self):
        return None

    def update(self, id, current_time, measurements):
        YawOffset = 0.0
        BladePitchAngles = [0.645, 0.645, 0.645]
        if (current_time >= 10.0) and (id == 1):
            YawOffset = 20.0

        print(f"Measurements: {measurements}")
        setpoints = dict({
            "ZMQ_YawOffset": YawOffset,
            "ZMQ_PitOffset(1)": BladePitchAngles[0],
            "ZMQ_PitOffset(2)": BladePitchAngles[1],
            "ZMQ_PitOffset(3)": BladePitchAngles[2]
        })
        return setpoints

if __name__ == "__main__":
    """Start the ZeroMQ server for wind farm control"""
    server = wfc_zmq_server("tcp://*:5555", timeout=60.0, verbose=True, logfile=None)
    # Provide the wind farm control algorithm as the wfc_controller method of the server
    server.wfc_controller = wfc_controller

    # Run the server to receive measurements and send setpoints
    server.runserver()

```

Figure 2.5: Example of a wind farm controller class used to facilitate the ZeroMQ interface.

Reading the wind turbine signals and sending the wind farm control setpoints are handled by the `wfc_zmq_server` class in ROSCO. The communication occurs on the network channel "tcp://*:5555" and if the wind farm controller receives no signal from any ROSCO clients for over 60 seconds then the wind farm controller will shut down (assuming that the simulation has either completed successfully or crashed).

While ZeroMQ has various server- and client-side examples on their website, MATLAB is not included. However, MATLAB remains a popular language of choice for the development of advanced control algorithms. In order to couple a MATLAB-based wind farm controller to ROSCO through ZeroMQ, JeroMQ - the Java-based implementation of ZeroMQ that MATLAB can leverage - should be used. However,

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Python is the preferred solution within SUDOCO, so the specific implementation in MATLAB is not prioritized.

3 Results

3.1 LES of reference wind farms

Table 2.1 gives an overview of the performed LES, which has gone into constructing the database. The database contains the following:

- Time series of turbine performance, include power production, operational parameters (e.g. rotational speed, pitch), aerodynamic loads, and deflections for all turbines.
- Planes of inflow velocity components extracted $1R$ upstream of all wind turbines.
- Horizontal planes of flow components extracted at hub height $170m$ and at top tip height $312m$.
- Vertical plane of flow components extracted at $x = 5,715m$, i.e. behind the wind farms and approximately $2R$ before the grid starts stretching.

The database has been built as reference and baseline scenarios for the subsequent wind farm control studies, but will also be utilized to train and calibrate faster engineering models which has lower fidelity than LES. Here, a high-level analysis will be performed on flow and turbine performance in terms of power production and examples of aerodynamic flapwise root bending moments to showcase the content of the database. All simulations have been run for $4,500sec$, where the initial $900sec$ of transient have been removed so all results in the following are based on one hour or $3,600sec$.

3.1.1 Wind Farm Flows

Figure 3.1 shows instantaneous and time-averaged streamwise wind speed for the CL-Windcon wind farm rotated 90° for three different grid levels and for the equidistant mesh region for an initial inversion height of $150m$. Please refer to Figure 2.3 for the full domain size. The instantaneous wind speed shown in the left column clearly show the turbulent wake flows including both small-scale turbulent structures and large-scale meandering. The turbulent structures are clearly more resolved on grid level 1, where the numerical cells are a factor 4 smaller in each direction, but qualitative the flows look very similar. This is even more the case for the time-averaged

wind speed for the three grid levels shown in the right column, which are very similar on average. Here, the induction upstream each turbine and the overall blockage between the turbines is evident. Finally, there are numerical wiggles clearly visible in both instantaneous and time-averaged figures for grid level 3, and only to a minor degree in the instantaneous flow towards the end of the equidistant region in grid level 2, while it is absent in the instantaneous and time-averaged wind speed at grid level 1. The cause of the wiggles has been investigated by performing simulations without turbines as well as simulations with stiff turbines operating in the domain to understand if the presence of the turbines introduce numerical instabilities, but wiggles remain. Therefore, the likely culprit is grid level 3 and to some degree level 2 being too coarse to properly resolve the flow, but it will require additional investigations in the future.

Figure 3.2 shows the time-averaged streamwise wind speed at hub height for different rotations of the CL-Windcon wind farm as well as the subset of the HKN wind farm with inflow corresponding to South-West for initial inversion height of 150m. The wakes and the mutual wake interaction is seen, particular for the aligned cases with 0° and 90°. For the unaligned cases, there are several half-wake scenarios, where the HKN is slightly offset. The wakes are also have a minor re-direction due to veer.

Figure 3.3 shows the corresponding time-averaged streamwise wind speed at hub height for different rotations of the CL-Windcon wind farm as well as the subset of the HKN wind farm with inflow corresponding to South-West for initial inversion height of 500m. Overall trends are qualitatively similar as the 150m-case, but three main differences appear. First, wakes are longer in the 500m-case compare to the 150m-case despite a higher turbulence intensity, see Figure 2.2. Second, the re-direction of the due to veer is absent in the 500m-case so the wakes are more straight. Third, the upstream blockage is slightly more severe in the 150m-case with a minor acceleration, where as it is more or less constant in the 500m-case.

Figure 3.1: Instantaneous and time-averaged streamwise wind speed for the CL-Windcon wind farm rotated 90° for three different grid levels and with initial inversion height of 150m.

Figure 3.2: Time-averaged streamwise wind speed for the CL-Windcon wind farm for different rotations as well as the HKN wind farm for initial inversion height of $150m$. All results are shown for the finest grid level and with wind from left to right.

Figure 3.3: Time-averaged streamwise wind speed for the CL-Windcon wind farm for different rotations as well as the HKN wind farm for initial inversion height of $500m$. All results are shown for the finest grid level and with wind from left to right.

3.1.2 Power Output and Turbine Loading

The mean power production of the CL-Windcon and HKN wind farms are shown in Figures 3.4 and 3.5, for all cases and all grid resolutions (3.4A and 3.5A) as well as the percentage difference in total power production relative to the highest grid resolution (3.4B and 3.5B).

Figure 3.4: 150m ABL height: A) Mean total power output for all cases, at all grid resolutions; B) Percentage difference in power output based on highest grid resolution for each case.

Figure 3.5: 500m ABL height: A) Mean total power output for all cases, at all grid resolutions; B) Percentage difference in power output based on highest grid resolution for each case.

The overall trend is that the total power production of the wind farms decreases with increasing grid resolution, except for the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm rotated 45° for the 150m boundary layer height, and the 90° rotation for the 500m boundary layer height. Considering Figures 3.4A and 3.5A, for both boundary layer heights

the lowest total power output is from the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm rotated 90° , as this results in the second and third row turbines operating in full wake, and with a shorter spacing than with the 0° rotation. The largest power output in the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm cases for both boundary layer heights is the 15° rotation, where all turbines operate in partial wake or out of wake entirely.

The percentage difference for each case based on the highest grid resolution is also shown in Figure 3.4B and 3.5B. The largest percentage difference relative to the finest grid resolution is 4.4%, occurring for the 15° rotation of the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm for the 500m boundary layer. Particularly in the 500m BL height results (Figure 3.5) it is clear that the lowest grid resolution performs worst in cases involving partial wake; the 15° , 30° and 45° rotations of the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm. For the 150m boundary layer height, as can be seen in the mean flow plots in Figure 3.2, wakes are additionally turned due to the strong veer in the inversion layer as the turbine rotors operate at rather than below the ABL height, and hence this trend is less apparent and the 0° case has similar grid dependency to the 15° and 30° .

The used grid resolutions will typically result in up to 1% differences in thrust coefficient C_T for a single turbine (Hodgson et al., 2021; Hodgson et al., 2023a), but the sensitivities can aggregate for some flow cases. The wake of each turbine is also influenced both by the change in thrust, and also by the lower grid resolution resolving the shear layer shed from the disc more coarsely, which leads to a slower wake recovery (Hodgson et al., 2023a; Hodgson et al., 2023b). Additionally, although the maximum difference in total wind farm power output due to grid resolution is 4.4%, the percentage difference between the power outputs of individual turbines occasionally varies much more than this aggregated figure. Therefore, when considering wind farm control scenarios where each turbine may be controlled differently, using appropriate grid resolution is very important to accurately assess the impact on wake flow and power output.

In Figures 3.6 and 3.7, the effect of wind direction on the CL-Windcon 3×3 wind farm is shown through plotting the power output of each turbine individually, using the data from the highest grid resolution for each case. The turbine numbering is based on the layout of 0° rotated wind farm, as shown in Figure 2.3. Turbine 1 is the lower left turbine (at the position with the smallest x and y). Turbines 2 and 3 count vertically upwards, making up the front row in the 0° rotation case, and counting continues by first increasing in y , and then increasing in x .

Figures 3.6 and 3.7 demonstrate the effect of wake losses on the power output of the turbines; in the 0° rotation case, turbines 1, 2 and 3 experience the undisturbed inflow and hence produce the largest power output, and then turbines in the subsequent rows (4-6 and 7-9) operate in wake and hence produce less. At a 15° rotation angle, the turbines are no longer aligned with the wind direction and the

Figure 3.6: The CL-Windcon 3 × 3 wind farm at 150m ABL height: Power output (mean and standard deviation) per turbine for all wind direction angles, at the highest grid resolution.

Figure 3.7: The CL-Windcon 3 × 3 wind farm at 500m ABL height: Power output (mean and standard deviation) per turbine for all wind direction angles, at the highest grid resolution.

power output of all turbines is similar as wake losses are substantially reduced, and the total wind farm power in Figures 3.4 and Figures 3.5 is increased. The lowest power output of any turbines in any case are turbines 2, 5 and 8 for the 90° rotation (corresponding to the middle row in the rotated setup), as the 90° rotation results in these turbines operating in full wake with a very short spacing between turbines. Comparing Figures 3.6 and 3.7, the influence of the inflow boundary layer height can be clearly seen. For a 500m boundary layer height (Figure 3.7), the rows of turbines in the 0° case (turbines 1-3, 4-6 and 7-9) have very similar power outputs, whereas

in the the equivalent 150m boundary layer case in Figure 3.6, there is much more variation between turbines 4-6 and 7-9 due to the turning of the wakes. Likewise, there are different trends between the 15°, 30° and 45° rotation cases.

Turbine loading and fatigue must also be considered in addition to power output when studying wind farm control strategies. The damage equivalent load (DEL) is used to quantify and compare the loading experienced by the turbine blades, and is shown for the flapwise bending moment (BM) in Figures 3.8 and 3.9 for the 150m and 500m boundary layer respectively. The flapwise BM DEL is calculated using a Wöhler coefficient of 10 at a frequency of 0.5 Hz, using 600s sampling intervals overlapping by 300s, for the full hour of data. The data for all blades are combined in the results shown.

The flapwise damage equivalent loads shows that turbines operating in wake or partial wake experience higher loading than those operating in freestream flow (as can be seen clearly by comparing turbines 1-3, 4-6 and 7-9 in the 0° rotation cases), due to the higher turbulence intensity present in wakes. Additionally, studying the flapwise DEL also displays the differences between wind farm rotations, boundary layer heights and grid resolutions. Generally, the coarser grid resolutions lead to an overestimation of damage equivalent loads in comparison to the finest grid. This is presumably because the coarser grid resolution does not resolve the wake turbulence as well, leading to a slower wake recovery and hence greater wake-induced loading on the turbines operating in wake. The coarser grid resolution also performs particularly poorly in turbines operating in partial wake, for example turbines 4, 5 and 8 in the 45° rotation of the CL-Windcon 3 × 3 wind farm, at 150m boundary layer height.

By comparing Figures 3.8 and 3.9, the difference between the two boundary layers is also clear. As described for Figures 3.6 and 3.7 (and as can be seen in the mean flow plots of Figures 3.2 and 3.3), the wake deflection which occurs for the 150m boundary layer height leads to turbines in the 15° and 45° rotations operating more in partial wake, whereas for the 500m height the wake flow does not directly impinge on the downstream turbines and the loading of all turbines is more similar. For the HKN wind farm this flow turning in the 150m boundary layer results in all turbines having similar DEL, while for the 500m boundary layer it is turbines 4 and 5 (at the highest x coordinates) which show a peak in DEL. The overall highest damage equivalent load experienced is the third row of turbines in the 90° rotation of the CL-Windcon 3 × 3 wind farm, due to the short spacing.

Figure 3.8: 150m ABL height: Flapwise Damage Equivalent Loads (mean and standard deviation) per turbine for all wind farm cases: A) 3x3 0deg; B) 3x3 15deg; C) 3x3 30deg; D) 3x3 45deg; E) 3x3 90deg; F) HKN.

Figure 3.9: 500m ABL height: Flapwise Damage Equivalent Loads (mean and standard deviation) per turbine for all wind farm cases: A) 3x3 0deg; B) 3x3 15deg; C) 3x3 30deg; D) 3x3 45deg; E) 3x3 90deg; F) HKN.

3.2 Demonstrating the wind farm controller interface in FAST.Farm

The wind farm controller interface is demonstrated through a FAST.Farm simulation with three IEA 22MW wind turbines, spaced approximately 5 rotor diameters apart. The IEA 22MW is a recurrent turbine throughout SUDOCO, and so is well suited for this demo. The simulation files and wind farm controller are gathered in a GitHub repository ¹, which includes a more detailed manual and video of the simulation.

Each turbine runs its own instance of ROSCO with ZeroMQ enabled. The specific settings for each turbine controller as specified in their DISCON.IN files are shown in Figure 3.10.

!----- ZeroMQ Interface -----	
"tcp://localhost:5555"	! ZMQ_CommAddress
2.000000	! ZMQ_UpdatePeriod
1	! ZMQ_ID

!----- ZeroMQ Interface -----	
"tcp://localhost:5555"	! ZMQ_CommAddress
2.000000	! ZMQ_UpdatePeriod
2	! ZMQ_ID

!----- ZeroMQ Interface -----	
"tcp://localhost:5555"	! ZMQ_CommAddress
2.000000	! ZMQ_UpdatePeriod
3	! ZMQ_ID

Figure 3.10: Turbine controller settings from DISCON.IN files: turbine 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

This means all turbines communicate with the wind farm controller over the same network port at an interval of 2 seconds. The wind farm controller used here can be found in the Python file `wake_steering_controller.py` in the github given above. Each exchange with a ROSCO controller will call the update function in the `wfc_controller` class. The wind farm controller follows the following sequence. Firstly, the farm controller saves the measurements from ROSCO to a local variable to preserve some sort of memory. Secondly, it optimizes the yaw angles to maximize the farm-wide power production. It could also optimize the blade pitch angles, but that function is empty for demonstration purposes. Finally, the setpoints are collected and sent to ROSCO. The optimisation of yaw angles is achieved through the `self.optimize_yaw_angles()`, which contains a yaw optimization algorithm from

¹https://github.com/SUDOCO-EU/windfarmcontroller_zeromq_demo/tree/main

the FLORIS repository². Thus, it loads a FLORIS model of the three-turbine wind farm and then performs the wake steering optimization.

To run the simulation, the wind farm controller and the OpenFAST simulation must be started in parallel. In Linux, this is done with the & operator. Figure 3.11 and Figure 3.12 demonstrate how the simulation develops by showing snapshots of the flow development and the time series of power and nacelle heading, respectively.

Figure 3.11: FAST.Farm flow results at 45, 120, and 900 seconds of simulation time.

Initially, all turbines are in baseline operation with zero yaw misalignment, while the wakes develop. Then, after 60 seconds of simulation time, the wake steering controller kicks in and applies yaw misalignment offsets. At 120 seconds, the turbines have achieved their optimal yaw offsets of 25 deg, 20 deg and 0 deg, respectively for turbines 1 through 3. This is shown in Figure 3.11, in the 120s snapshot. In Figure 3.12 we also see a small drop in power production for both turbines 1 and

²<https://github.com/NREL/floris>

Figure 3.12: Time series of power and nacelle heading (yaw) from FAST.Farm.

2 because there are now yaw-misaligned with the incoming wind.

Finally, the wakes propagate, and the turbines find an equilibrium in their power production. Clearly, the power production of turbine 3 is significantly higher at the end of the simulation (when both wakes of T1 and T2 have been steered away from the row) than halfway the simulation (when full wake deflection has not yet been achieved).

Please see the repository for a full video of the simulation.

4 Conclusion

Deliverable D1.1 of the SUDOCO project provides a substantial LES database. The database has been constructed using a newly developed coupling framework, Dynamiks, which provides interface between the high-fidelity flow solver, EllipSys3D, and the high-fidelity aero-servo-elastic tool, HAWC2. The database contains flow and operational data for a scaled version of the CL-Windcon wind farm consisting of 3×3 IEA22MW turbines subject to different wind directions as well as a scaled version of a subset of 10 IEA22MW turbines corresponding to the South-West corner of the HKN wind farm. All simulations have been run for two different boundary layer heights, one above the rotor and one with within the rotor area. Furthermore, the simulations have been run on three different grid levels to provide insights into the sensitivity of power production and damage equivalent load estimation relative to the grid resolution. Overall, the trends are qualitative comparable for different grid levels and for different boundary layers, but there are clear indications that power production decrease with increasing grid resolution for most cases.

This report also showcase the implementation of a communication interface between the overall wind farm controller and the ROSCO controller for each individual turbine. The implementation is tested and first results shown using FAST.Farm, which provides optimization of individual yaw angles to improve power production of the wind farm.

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